

SITE SPHINX	DATE 6/25/79	AREA NE	SQUARE N3/E1	PAGE
 Feature No.	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top: 10.61	Bottom: 1046.5
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter: 10 cm	Width:	Length:	Depth: 4.5 cm	

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions	
1	SAND	Grey Brown	Packed	Fine	T 6 Very Small Fragments	Lm ✓ Small Fraggs 1 cm	Gp
						Gr	Char ^{Few} Small Flecks
						Do	
					D 0	Ba	Greenish Fibrous Dung Like Material
						Al	
						Other Fiber (Straw-like, fine, thin)	
2	Gypsum	off white	Packed (on bottom thin residue)	Grainy	T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char Fine Flecks
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/ 1 No./ 28	B&W: Roll/ 1 No./ 23
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DRAWN	Area Plan: 1:20	Feature Plan: 1:2	Sections: 1:2
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: Probably excavated NS 78 and refilled during year. Indicated by mortar left on bottom